

NETWORK INFORMATION PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Our life is changing, technologies are changing in various fields of human activity, including in the field of information technology. The teaching methods that existed until now are outdated, and they have been replaced by new ones, which are becoming a suitable tool for interested learning of schoolchildren. One of the promising ways of getting education in our time is online learning, using the opportunities provided by modern telecommunication technologies and, in particular, the Internet. Currently, students have the opportunity to access the richest information resources of networks and the opportunity to work together with students from other countries, within the framework of teleconferences - to discuss problems with almost the whole world. Such a prospect of cooperation creates a strong motivation for their independent, cognitive activities in groups and individually, regardless of time and space zones. Also one of the most demanded components of network technologies is the forum. Forum is a special software for thematic communication. Its job is for users to create topics in sections and then have discussions within those topics. Forum participants can be students, teachers, heads of educational institutions and other participants. This is a place on the Internet where people who are united by one hobby or idea gather and communicate on a topic of interest to them. They help each other with advice and tips, exchange life experiences, support each other. Currently, the popularity of forums is declining. Their role is increasingly shifting to social networks. Electronic document management - allows you to organize the correct joint work on documents. The functioning of electronic document management in the organization allows you to avoid confusion and errors in the preparation. Currently, there are document management systems based on web 2.0 technologies that make it possible to keep a chronology of document versions, assign different access rights to a document to users, and ensure simultaneous editing of a document by several users at once. Information technology tools allow students to expand their horizons through modern telecommunication environments, learn how to select information, transform it in accordance with the content, and systematize the presentation of this information on the Web. The role of the telecommunications environment in education is, of course, enormous. At present, according to the new educational

standards, the teacher ceases to transfer knowledge in a ready-made form, but creates conditions for children to acquire knowledge themselves in the process of telecommunication environment using computer technology in working on tasks directly related to real life problems and to be competitive in the educational services market. . Therefore, at present, the teacher becomes a consultant, the coordinator who is addressed not by position, but as an authoritative source of information, as an expert. Network technologies make it possible to use various software tools in the educational process that increase interest in the subject and, as a result, improve the quality of education. These are video conferences that provide interaction between people who are at a considerable distance or who are not present at a certain time in a given place. For example, the "lecture" mode allows you to organize lectures, seminars and regular lessons. The teacher can conduct training sessions using a virtual whiteboard, calling the corresponding student to it. Other participants can work simultaneously with the board. This feature is useful for most users. The main objectives of the videoconference are: the ability to argue statements and evaluate both oneself and the interlocutor; the ability to conduct a dialogue within a certain time; to teach to understand and hear the problem of another expressed in another language and be able to help solve it or give an answer in the language of another interlocutor. Video lessons allow you to raise the level of education higher than any book, and in order to use video lessons in the classroom or outside of class, you must use network software. Video lessons allow you to give the material in full and show everything that the program requires, without violating the basic principle of learning - the principle of visibility. Thus, the use of local computer networks at school shows that the informatization of the educational process is moving with the times. In addition, the use of networked forms of learning contributes to the improvement of the learning process, increases motivation and cognitive activity, positively affects the development of the intellectual and emotional spheres of students and, as a result, increases the effectiveness of learning.

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